

ISSN- 0301-1216

Indian J. Prev. Soc. Med. Vol. 56, No.1, 2025

Assessment of Sociodemographic Profile and Lifestyle practices in patients with obesity

Shraddha Tiwari¹, Mukta Singh², L.P. Meena³

ABSTRACT

Obesity is a chronic, progressive and relapsing disease characterized by the presence of excessive adiposity that negatively affects health and social well-being. This study aimed to assess the socio-demographic profile, lifestyle practices and eating habits of obese patients and their association with Body Mass Index (BMI). It was a cross-sectional study, where 130 obese patients aged 20-60 were enrolled and assessed by the self-constructed questionnaire through an interview schedule. The findings of this investigation indicated that the majority of respondents, 41.5% were classified as lower middle class. About 40.8% of respondents did not follow a consistent eating pattern. A substantial majority of the respondents comprising 73.8%, were female. This study found significant associations between education, monthly income, and eating habits with BMI ($p < 0.05$). The study concluded that there are significant associations between education, monthly income and eating habits with BMI in obese patients. These findings highlight the importance of addressing socio-demographic factors and lifestyle practices in managing obesity effectively.

Keywords: Obesity, Socio-demographic profile, Lifestyle practices, BMI.

Author(s) Details:

1. Research Scholar, Department of Home Science, Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi- 221 005
2. Professor, Department of Home Science, Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi- 221 005.
3. Professor & Head, Department of General Medicine, Institute of Medical Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi- 221 005.

Corresponding Address:

Shraddha Tiwari, Research Scholar, Department of Home Science, Mahila Mahavidyalaya, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi- 221 005; **Email:** shraddha5985@bhu.ac.in

Citation: Tiwari S, Singh M, Meena LP. Assessment of Sociodemographic Profile and Lifestyle practices in patients with obesity. Indian J Prev Soc Med, 2025; 56 (1): **127-133**.

DOI: <http://doi.org/----->

Sequence of Article:

Submission: 23.01.2025 | Revision: 12.02.2025 | Accepted: 21.02.2025 | Published: 31.03.2025

Prior Publication: Nil; Source of Funding: Nil; Conflicts of Interest: None, Article # 669/941

Introduction

Obesity has emerged as a significant public health challenge worldwide, with its prevalence tripling since the 1970s.¹ Obesity and overweight are characterized by excessive fat deposition in the body,² which can impair health and increase the possibility of developing a range of associated conditions like coronary heart disease, type 2 diabetes, hypertension, renal disease, dyslipidaemia, asthma, insulin resistance, obstructive sleep apnea and several types of cancer.³ Obesity is associated with several negative health outcomes that can be improved by long-term weight reduction.

In 2022, obesity affected approximately one out of every eight individuals worldwide. Recent studies indicates that over 2.5 billion people globally are overweight, with 890 million of them classified as obese .⁴ The adverse effects are more prevalent in developing nations due to sedentary lifestyles, consumption of energy-dense foods (i.e., unhealthy eating habits), limited access to healthcare, and insufficient financial support ⁵.

The ICMR-INDIAB 2015 study found that the prevalence of central obesity ranges from 16.9% to 36.3%, while obesity prevalence spans from 11.8% to 31.3%. In India, abdominal obesity is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease⁶.

Overweight and obese subjects are associated with altered lipid levels, called dyslipidemia. This is an alarming risk factor for coronary and cerebro-vascular disease development⁷. Many research investigations showed that being obese or overweight is linked with hyperlipidemia, which has low HDL and high LDL characteristics.

Weight management strategies for treating obesity involve a wide range of lifestyle changes (including dietary, physical activity and psychological components) to change unhealthy behaviours, promote weight loss, and avoid chronic weight gain.

One of the key areas of interest in obesity research is the socio-demographic profile of affected individuals. Socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, income, education, and occupation are important determinants of health outcomes and behaviours. These factors can influence dietary patterns, physical activity levels and access to healthcare, thereby impacting the risk of obesity and associated illnesses

Objectives

1. To assess the socio-demographic profile and lifestyle practices of patients with obesity.
2. To evaluate the association between various sociodemographic variables, lifestyle practices and eating habits with BMI.

Methodology

Ethical Clearance: The study's ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Science (BHU) and Ref No: ECR/226/Indt/UP/2014/RR-22. Informed consent was taken from all the participants with the assurance that their identity would not be revealed and only if they agreed to participate in the study were then asked questions regarding the study objectives asked to them.

Study Design: A cross-sectional study was conducted in the General Medicine Outpatient Department (OPD) of a tertiary health care centre, where 130 obese patients aged 20-60 years were enrolled. The study was conducted from July to September 2024.

Method of sampling -The purposive sampling method (non-probability) was used for the sample selection.

Sample Selection - Respondents were selected under the category of obesity as per the WHO (2000) Asian cut-off points (BMI ≥ 25.00 kg/m²). These respondents were screened for their initial anthropometric measurements of height, body weight and body mass index (BMI) levels. These obese patients were selected in consultation with the doctors based on their BMI value, blood pressure level, and biochemical parameters drawn from their medical reports. Respondents having severe complications, pregnant and lactating mothers, and respondents who were unwilling to participate in the study were excluded from the study.

Tools and Techniques- Data were collected using a self-administered pretested questionnaire through an interview schedule that included various sections on socio-demographic information B. G. Prasad scale (updated 2023), dietary habits, medical history, physical activity, family history of non-communicable diseases, and other lifestyle practices. Body Mass Index (BMI) was calculated using height and weight measurements. Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 25.0 version was used to process and analyse the data. Frequency and percentages were used to show descriptive statistics (for categorical data).

Results and Discussion

Table -1 show that the respondents were distributed across different age groups with the highest percentage 32.3% in the 41-50 years age group. The 31-40 years group followed with 24.6%. Most of the respondents belonged to rural areas followed by 72.3%. A study on the dietary and lifestyle risk factors for obesity in young people showed that middle-aged adults (41–50 years old) frequently have higher BMIs because of lifestyle variables.⁸ A significant majority of the respondents were female 73.8%. A study was carried out to investigate the characteristics that are particular to gender and impact obesity in older individuals in India. It was discovered that women had a larger likelihood of being overweight or obese than men and that money, higher education, and urban residency were important contributing variables.⁹

<p>A significant portion of respondents had completed higher secondary education 35.4%. Occupationally, respondents were diverse with the largest group being clerical, farm, or shop workers 27.7%, followed by other occupations 26.9%. The monthly income distribution showed that 41.5% of respondents belonged to the lower middle class. Marital status data indicated that most respondents were married 68.5%. The type of family data showed that a majority of respondents lived in a nuclear family 64.6%. A study that examined the relationship between environmental and sociodemographic factors and obesity indicated that the risk of obesity was significantly affected by age, sex, income, education level, and household composition.¹⁰</p> <p>The data collected from 130 participants is summarized below to highlight significant differences.</p>	Table-1: Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents (N=130)			
	Demographic Variables		No.	%
	Age (years)	21-30	26	20.0
		31-40	32	24.6
		41-50	42	32.3
		51-60	30	23.1
	Gender	Male	34	26.2
		Female	96	73.8
	Education	Illiterate	18	13.8
		Primary	24	18.5
		High school	12	9.2
		Higher Secondary	46	35.4
		Higher education	30	23.1
	Occupation	Professional	12	9.2
		Semi Professional	30	23.1
		Clerical/farm/shop	36	27.7
		Skilled worker	17	13.1
		Others	35	26.9
	Socio-economic status	Upper Class	6	4.6
		Upper Middle Class	30	23.1
Middle Class		29	22.3	
Lower Middle Class		54	41.5	
Lower Class		11	8.5	
Marital Status	Married	89	68.5	
	Unmarried	35	26.9	
	Widow/ Divorced	6	4.6	
Type of Family	Joint	46	35.4	
	Nuclear	84	64.6	
Area of Residence	Rural	94	72.3	
	Urban	36	27.7	

Table-2 shows that the majority of respondents belonged 30-34.9 kg/m² BMI range 53.1%, followed by those in the 25-29.9 kg/m² range 43.1% and a smaller proportion were 35-39.9 kg/m² range 3.8%.

Table-2: BMI of Obese Patients (N=130)

BMI	No.	%
Obesity > 24.9 kg/m ²		
25-29.9	56	43.1
30-34.9	69	53.1
35.39.9	5	3.8

Figure-1, shows that among obesity-related comorbidities, hypertension was the most prevalent condition, affecting 27.7 percent of obese patients. It was followed by dyslipidaemia 17.7%, diabetes mellitus 13.8%, hyperuricemia 7.7%, thyroid 6.2 %, and pre-diabetes 4.6%. Additionally, 22.3% of the patients reported other problems, such as 12% shortness of breath and 10.3% with more than one co-morbidity. Obesity and overweight increase the risk of several diseases, such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, and hyperuricemia¹¹.

Figure-1 – Obesity related Comorbidities

Table-3: Association of BMI with the Socio-Demographic variables (N=130)

Demographic Variables		Number and percentage of respondents		P value
		No.	%	
Age (years)	21-30	26	20.0	0.000
	31-40	32	24.6	
	41-50	42	32.3	
	51-60	30	23.1	
Gender	Male	34	26.2	0.002
	Female	96	73.8	
Education	No literate	18	13.8	0.000
	Primary	24	18.5	
	High school	12	9.2	
	Higher Secondary	46	35.4	
	Higher Education	30	23.1	
Occupation	Professional	12	9.2	0.000
	Semi Professional	30	23.1	
	Clerical/farm/shop	36	27.7	
	Skilled worker	17	13.1	
	Others	35	26.9	
Marital status	Married	89	68.5	0.088
	Unmarried	35	26.9	
	Widow/Divorced	cc6	cv4.6	
Type of family	Joint	46	35.4	0.003
	Nuclear	84	64.6	
Area of Residence	Rural	94	72.3	0.000
	Urban	36	27.7	

Table-3 revealed that there was a significant association between various socio-demographic profiles like age, education level, occupation, monthly income, area of residence, and type of family with BMI (p<0.05). A study examined that age significantly influences BMI, with different age groups showing varying BMI trends. The study revealed that BMI increased with

age up to a certain point, after which it either stabilized or decreased.¹² There was no statistically significant relationship between BMI and either gender or marital status ($p>0.05$).

Table-4, suggested that a majority of respondents did not smoke 81.5%. Most respondents did not consume alcohol 86.2%. The majority of respondents were engaged in light exercise 82.3%. A substantial proportion of respondents had a family history of such non-communicable diseases 44.6%. Back pain, Numbness, Tingling, Stabbing, Joint pain and Family History of non-communicable diseases were significantly associated with BMI in obese patients ($p<0.05$). However, there is no significant association between smoking and alcoholism and BMI ($p>0.05$). Numerous studies have found a statistically significant link between BMI and physical activity levels.¹³ Adopting healthy lifestyle practices such as engaging in regular exercise and avoiding smoking was linked to a notable reduction in mortality and enhanced BMI outcomes.¹⁴

Table-4: Lifestyle-related habits and their association with BMI (N=130)

Variables		No.	%	P value
Smoke	Yes	24	18.5	0.470
	No	106	81.5	
Alcohol	Yes	18	13.8	0.370
	No	112	86.2	
Exercise Activity	Light	107	82.3	0.000
	Moderate	11	8.5	
	Vigorous	12	9.2	
Back pain	Yes	60	46.2	0.023
	No	70	53.8	
Numbness, Tingling, Stabbing	Yes	71	54.6	0.053
	No	59	45.4	
Joint pain	Yes	66	50.8	0.032
	No	64	49.2	
Family History of non-communicable diseases	Yes	58	44.6	0.039
	No	72	55.4	

Table-5 depicts that 40% of participants were vegetarians and 60% were non-vegetarians. The majority of participants, 45.4%, consumed 2-3 liters of fluids daily, around 40.8% had no regular eating pattern, and approximately 54.6% of participants admitted to experiencing periods of binge eating. Eating habits or patterns like food habits, fluid intake, meals per day, and regular eating patterns were significantly associated with BMI in obese patients ($p<0.05$). There is no significant association between Binge eating and BMI ($p>0.05$). Obesity and binge eating had an apparent correlation; binge eating frequently led to weight increase. According to studies, people who suffer from binge eating often eat excessive amounts of food in a short length of time, resulting in an energy surplus that leads to weight gain.¹⁵

Table-5: Eating habits and its association with BMI (N=130)

Variables		No.	%	P value
Food Habit	Vegetarian	52	40.0	0.002
	Non- Vegetarian	78	60.0	
Fluid intake	0-1l	6	4.6	0.006
	1-2 l	24	18.5	
	2-3l	59	45.4	
	3-4l	35	26.9	
	4-5l	6	4.6	
Meals per day	More than 3 meals (with healthy snacks)	6	4.6	0.002
	3 meals	47	36.2	
	2 meals or less	24	18.5	
	No regular eating pattern	53	40.8	
Binge Eating	Yes	71	54.6	0.114
	No	59	45.4	

Furthermore, binge eating was associated with psychological factors, including body dissatisfaction and low self-esteem, which further influenced obesity indicators.¹⁶ Many studies have identified a significant link between BMI and unhealthy eating behaviors, including irregular meal patterns and inadequate fluid intake.¹⁷ A study was conducted to examine the association between healthy lifestyle habits, such as regular fluid intake and eating patterns, and BMI. The study revealed that these habits were pivotal in maintaining a healthy BMI.¹⁴ A systematic review and meta-analysis showed that behavioral interventions such as making dietary modifications and establishing regular meal patterns are effective in managing obesity and lowering BMI.¹⁸

Conclusions

This cross-sectional study investigated the socio-demographic profile, lifestyle practices, and eating habits of obese patients in a tertiary healthcare setting. Overweight and obesity are linked to a range of risk factors, including unhealthy lifestyle practices, educational influences, socioeconomic status, poor dietary habits, and insufficient physical activity. The results showed significant associations between BMI and factors such as age, education, occupation, monthly income, type of family, physical activity, back pain, joint pain, family history of non-communicable diseases, food habits, fluid intake and meal patterns.

The prevalence of obesity-related co-morbidities was high, with hypertension being the most common condition. These findings highlight the importance of addressing lifestyle and dietary factors in obesity management and prevention strategies. Targeted interventions focusing on promoting healthy habits, physical activity and balanced eating patterns may help mitigate the risk of obesity and related diseases in this population.

Recommendations

Future research should prioritize longitudinal designs and diverse sampling strategies to further elucidate the complex relationships between socio-demographic factors, lifestyle practices, eating habits and obesity. Developing tailored interventions and investigating the impact of socioeconomic factors on obesity management.

References

1. Blüher M. Obesity: global epidemiology and pathogenesis. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*, 2019, 15(5), 288-298.
2. World Health Organization. International Association of Study of Obesity, International Obesity Task Force: The Asia-Pacific Perspective. Redefining Obesity and Its Treatment. 2000, www.wpro.who.int/nutrition/documents/Redefining_obesity/en/.
3. Savini, Catani MV, Evangelista D, Gasperi V, Avigliano L. Obesity-Associated Oxidative Stress: Strategies Finalized to Improve Redox State. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2013 May; 14(5):10497-538.
4. World Health Organization (2024). Obesity and overweight. 2024, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>.
5. Hill JO, Wyatt HR, & Peters JC. Energy balance and obesity. *Circulation*, 2012, 126(1), 126-132.
6. Pradeepa R, Anjana RM, Joshi SR, Bhansali A, Deepa M, Joshi PP & ICMR-INDIAB Collaborative Study Group. Prevalence of generalized & abdominal obesity in urban & rural India-the ICMR-INDIAB Study (Phase-I) [ICMR-INDIAB-3]. *The Indian Journal of Medical Research*, 2015, 142(2), 139.
7. Gotto Jr, AM. Triglyceride is a risk factor for coronary artery disease. *The American journal of cardiology*, 1998, 82 (8), 22-25.
8. Lee KX, Quek KF, & Ramadas A. Dietary and lifestyle risk factors of obesity among young adults: A scoping review of observational studies. *Current Nutrition Reports*, 2023, 12(4), 733-743.
9. Saha A, Mandal B, Muhammad T, Barman P, & Ahmed W. Gender-specific determinants of overweight and obesity among older adults in India: evidence from a cross-sectional survey, 2017-18. *BMC Public Health*, 2023, 23(1), 2313.
10. Pou SA, Diaz, MDP, Velázquez GA, & Aballay LR. Sociodemographic disparities and contextual factors in obesity: updated evidence from a National Survey of Risk Factors for Chronic Diseases. *Public Health Nutrition*, 2022, 25(12), 3377-3389.
11. Guh DP, Zhang W, Bansback N, Amarsi Z, Birmingham CL, & Anis AH. The incidence of co-morbidities related to obesity and overweight: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Public Health*, 2009, 9, 1-20.
12. Karlsson, IK, Lehto K, Gatz M, Reynolds CA, & Dahl Aslan AK. Age-dependent effects of body mass index across the adult life span on the risk of dementia: a cohort study with a genetic approach. *BMC Medicine*, 2020, 18, 1-11.

13. Hossain S, Hossain MS, Anjum A, Ahmed F, Hossain MF & Uddin ME. Risk modelling of non-communicable diseases using socio-demographic characteristics, lifestyle and family disease history among university students in Bangladesh. *Journal of Public Health*, 2018, 26, 531-543.
14. Matheson EM, King DE, & Everett CJ. Healthy lifestyle habits and mortality in overweight and obese individuals. *The Journal of the American Board of Family Medicine*, 2012, 25(1), 9-15.
15. Saruco E, & Pleger, B. (2021). A systematic review of obesity and binge eating associated impairment of the cognitive inhibition system. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 2021, 8, 609012.
16. Lehto R, Ålgars M, Lommi S, Leppänen MH & Viljakainen H. Determinants of binge eating and its impact on indicators of obesity among Finnish adolescents-a cohort study. *Journal of Eating Disorders*, 2024, 12(1), 210.
17. LG, RC, LZ RS, & EM GD. Overweight and obesity in Colombian college students and its association with physical activity. *Nutricion Hospitalaria*, 2014, 31(2), 629-636.
18. Madigan CD, Graham HE, Sturgiss E, Kettle VE, Gokal K, Biddle G, & Daley AJ. Effectiveness of weight management interventions for adults delivered in primary care: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *BMJ*, 2022, 377.